

Do foundation models have local knowledge? A case study on bicycle routing in Graz

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Abstract

Local knowledge is often the best source of information to make decisions about a certain locality. We have advanced models of the environment in network models, map databases, and satellite and street-view imagery, and yet these models are static replicas of the environment that often fail to capture deeper semantic nuances. In our experience, we find this to be especially true when it comes to bicycle routing applications in cities with complex layouts, Graz being one such example. Even though they can be shortest paths, routes recommended by routing engines like Google Maps are often not the ones that the local population are taking. We believe that foundation models, with their ability to extract useful information from large amounts of unstructured data (and in different modalities) have the ability to learn and exhibit the local knowledge that is currently missing from the popular routing engines. Thus, we investigate the recommended routes from two different sources - conventional network routing engines and the foundation models - and evaluate them against our local knowledge of the city of Graz.

Keywords

local knowledge, routing, large language models (LLMs), foundation models, OpenStreetMap, GeoAI

1. Introduction

When I moved to Graz recently I was once again facing a familiar issue – trying my best to navigate the unfamiliar streets with no local knowledge nor prior experience and only a smartphone “maps” application to help me. I spent weeks planning my first bike trip to the office and was confused by the (shortest) paths recommended by routing applications - as even with my limited local knowledge I was able to notice issues in each recommendation, be it busy tram lines along the way, or the request to take too many turns along the way. When I showed this to my friend who is a local, he confirmed that the recommended routes make little sense and described the route I should take. I took his advice, and was astonished by the number of other (presumably local) cyclists who took that same route - nearly everyone commuting in the same direction as me was on this route, even though it is not recommended by any application I have prompted.

This anecdotal example is not isolated, but confirmed and shared by many others I discussed the cycling routes in Graz with. People who have local knowledge of the city seem to be very efficient in recognizing small nuances that can make a big difference when traveling by bicycle. These may include the amount of traffic (be it cars, pedestrians, trams, other bicycles), number of traffic lights (and sometimes even their timings), quality of the pavement, allowed or forbidden sections (e.g., bicycles are forbidden in parks, but there are a few exemptions), recent changes and disruptions (e.g., due to events or construction), shaded segments on hot days, scenery, and so on.

The problem with conventional routing applications is that it is impossible to declaratively model all of the nuances (some even subjective) a person with local knowledge considers when navigating their environment. They are based on vector representations of street networks with limited semantic information (e.g., existence and type of bicycle path, and sometimes slope and pavement quality) and

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always operate on the assumption that this data is correct and complete. Paired with a deterministic shortest path algorithm like Dijkstra, this creates a rigid approach that can hardly succeed in all cases when the best route is not also (one of) the shortest.

On the contrary, the learned representations in foundation models (FM) have the ability to capture almost unlimited nuances and dimensions of a certain theme. Because they can synthesize information (and maybe even knowledge) from unstructured data sources, they have the potential to acquire much more local knowledge based on books, websites, documents, forums, travel blogs, and other similar sources, compared to declarative street network models.

Thus, in this study we hypothesize that *“foundation models are able to learn local knowledge and utilize it real-world applications such as bicycle routing”*. We investigate this hypothesis with the task of bicycle routing in the city of Graz, where we compare routes generated by local knowledge (i.e., locals), a routing algorithm, and an FM. Our contributions are:

- we bring to the forefront the study of local knowledge in FMs,
- we propose a methodology for quantitative and qualitative evaluation of local knowledge in FMs in the context of bicycle routing.

2. Related Work

Routing algorithms are outstanding at solving well-defined, static problems but fall short of capturing dynamic, semantic, and people-oriented aspects of navigation in real world. To address these limitations, it is necessary to integrate semantic data, local knowledge, and adaptive models [1].

FMs are large-scale, adaptable AI systems trained on extensive, diverse datasets which enables them to perform a broad spectrum of tasks across various fields. Their scale not only affects performance but also unlocks capabilities that emerge once models surpass a size threshold. While FMs are partly task-agnostic, applying them to geospatial contexts reveals significant challenges: limited exposure to geospatial data formats, the specialized nature of geospatial tasks, and the inherently local, regional, or contextual characteristics of geographic information. These constraints necessitate Geospatial FMs (GeoFMs), which can enable a broader range of geospatial downstream applications [2].

Numerous studies analyze the geospatial knowledge encoded in FMs for downstream geospatial tasks. Manvi et al. [3] demonstrate that the vast knowledge compressed in large language models (LLMs) from internet corpora can be leveraged for geospatial prediction tasks, and Gao et al. [4] introduce LOCALBENCH, a benchmark dataset to systematically evaluate LLMs on county-level local knowledge across the United States, highlighting potential and gaps in capturing localized context.

The capabilities of (Geo)FMs extend to spatial question answering [5], spatial analysis [6], and spatial cognition [7]. A closely related downstream task to routing is the understanding of geospatial semantics, which Ji et al. [8] investigate by assessing LLMs’ ability to reason with topological spatial relations, underscoring both the promise and limitations of LLMs particularly when novel data modalities, such as geospatial vector or network data, are involved. One proposed solution is to utilize LLMs as agents, enabling more dynamic and context-aware interactions with geospatial data [2].

This paper focuses on the downstream task of routing, an area studied by Yang et al. [7], who analyze the ability of FMs to handle spatial cognition tasks by examining three types of knowledge: landmark knowledge, routing knowledge, and survey knowledge [9] which enables humans to navigate by identifying landmarks, building routes between them, and developing mental maps of spaces. While Yang et al. demonstrate that LLMs exhibit only limited spatial cognition abilities in experimental settings, Roberts et al. [10], highlight the potential of FMs for generating routes and navigation instructions, thereby pointing the way toward route-planning systems that more closely resemble those of humans.

3. Methodology

To assess the ability of FMs to exhibit local knowledge, we employ a routing task between a set of origin and destination (OD) pairs, expressed as points. We use manually drawn routes as the representation of

Figure 1: Workflow depicting the individual steps of our Methodology.

the local knowledge in this task, and compare them to the routes generated by a routing engine and an FM. The overall workflow of our approach is shown in Figure 1.

We retrieved Points of Interest (POIs) for our study area (Graz, Austria) from OpenStreetMap (OSM) using the tags "amenity" = {"pub", "museum", "library"} and "tourism" = {"attraction", "museum"}. POIs with missing or empty "name" entries and non-Point geometries were filtered out. Resulting set comprised of 50 pubs, 44 libraries, 19 museums, and 15 attractions. We then generated 33 unique OD pairs by randomly sampling pairs of POIs with a minimum Euclidean distance of 2 km between them.

To incorporate human expertise, two authors with in-depth local knowledge of Graz's cycling infrastructure manually drew routes between 33 OD pairs in QGIS, each drawing a different set of routes without overlaps. They used OSM basemap as a spatial reference and provided qualitative comments to justify their choices, such as preferences for bike lanes or avoidance of high-traffic areas. The authors were blind to other generated routes to prevent bias.

As a representation of a routing engine with the implementation of the shortest path algorithm, we computed routes using the OpenRouteService (ORS) API with the "cycling-regular" profile, which prioritizes bicycle-friendly paths. The API returned the geometric representation of each route.

Finally, we generated FM routes with the latest reasoning model from OpenAI – gpt-5.5. We employed two prompting strategies – *v1*) providing the model with POI names and coordinates of origin and destination, and *v2*) providing only the reverse-geocoded address of the origin and destination points. Another notable distinction is that we asked the model in the *v1* setting to only return street names and avoid any additional context, while we did not impose this restriction in the *v2* setting (see Table 1).

The generated routing directions were then manually digitized in QGIS, while also noting any issues and hallucinations that have occurred.

4. Results

Figure 2 shows the lengths of all 33 routes across the four different route sources. Overall, the ORS routes most consistently show similar lengths to the manually drawn routes, while FM-routes show high variation. The figure also shows with red hatch which FM-routes were deemed invalid during the manual vectorization process – usually due to logical inconsistency in the route such as a suggested turn between two streets that in reality do not intersect.

Figure 3 shows the overlap between generated and manually drawn (reference) routes – as a ratio of the reference route, and the relationship to the Euclidean distance between the origin and destination points. We expected to see lower overlap ratios in longer routes compare to the shorter ones, but, contrary to our assumption, there is no such correlation visible. This indicates that OD distance does not affect the similarity of generated routes to the local knowledge (i.e., manually drawn routes).

Figure 4 shows the overlap between generated and manually drawn routes as a ratio of the reference

Setting	Prompt type	Prompt text
v1	system	You are a person living in Graz, Austria, and you help me find the best cycling routes using your local knowledge. You will get origin and destination name and coordinates. Return a clear step-by-step route with street names only. Do not ask follow-up questions.
v1	user	Give me the best cycling route from Pizzeria Da Vinci (47.0541793, 15.4442239) to Alte Galerie Schloss Eggenberg (47.0736876, 15.3912171).
v2	system	You are a person living in Graz, Austria, and you help me find the best cycling routes using your local knowledge. You will get origin and destination addresses. Return a complete step-by-step route. Do not ask follow-up questions.
v2	user	Give me the best cycling route from Pizzeria Da Vinci, Pomisgasse, 8010, Pomisgasse, Graz to Alte Galerie Schloss Eggenberg, 90, Eggenberger Allee, 8020, Eggenberger Allee, Graz.

Table 1

Examples of system and user prompts in the two prompt settings – v1 and v2.

Figure 2: Comparison of the 33 routes by length. Manually drawn routes were used as the ground truth reference in evaluation. The red hatch is added to indicate AI-generated routes that are deemed invalid.

route (Y-axis) and as a ratio of the generated (i.e., evaluated) route (X-axis). It shows several instances of invalid FM routes with the X value of 1.0, meaning that these routes were following the reference routes exactly until one point where they have lost their validity and further digitization was no longer possible. Figure 5 shows the map of the *gpt-5.5 v1 (Invalid)* route with overlap ratio of 0.42, and the reverse overlap ratio of 1.0. In this example, the generated route follows the reference route until approximately half way, when the generated directions suggest a turn into a street that does not intersect the current street.

Table 2 shows the statistical parameters of the overlap and reverse overlap between generated and reference routes. This confirms that FM routes show overall higher variability with higher standard deviations than ORS routes. Interestingly, it can also be observed that the maximum overlap and reverse overlap scores are higher for the FM routes, indicating that in specific OD pairs they were able to emulate the local knowledge exhibited in the manually drawn routes better than the routing engine of the ORS.

5. Conclusion and future work

We investigated the ability of FMs to exhibit local knowledge within the context of bicycle routing. Our approach compares local knowledge-based routes drawn by locals, routes generated by a routing

Figure 3: Similarity (overlap) of generated routes to the manually drawn routes and its relationship to the Euclidean distance between the origin and the destination points.

Figure 4: Similarity (overlap) of generated routes to the manually drawn routes expressed relative to the length of the reference (i.e., manually drawn) route (Y-axis) and relative to the length of the evaluated (i.e., generated) route (X-axis).

engine from the OpenRoutingService, and routes generated by the state of the art foundation model from OpenAI – gpt-5.5. These methods were compared on 33 OD pairs in Graz, Austria that were randomly sampled from the OpenStreetMap POIs. The results indicate that ORS routes align better to the manually drawn routes on the average, but the FM generated routes show more potential with higher maximum alignment values (Table 2). This is caused by many invalid FM routes that lose logical validity at a certain point by suggesting a turn that is not possible (e.g., into a street that does not intersect the current street). In particular, three types of errors have been observed:

1. Streets that are logically part of the route and are correctly named and listed in right order, but are missing one or more connecting elements to the next valid street segment.
2. Locations described from a geographically different direction of arrival which lead to contradictory instructions; e.g., a square would need to be crossed to reach the next valid street segment, but the instructions also state, *“If you reach the main tram area at Jakominiplatz, you’ve gone slightly*

Figure 5: Example where a route generated with gpt-5.5 v1 follows the manually drawn route exactly, but then becomes invalid as it suggests the user to turn from Annenstraße to Eggenberger Allee, but these two streets do not intersect.

	overlap ORS	reverse overlap ORS	overlap gpt-5.5 v1	reverse overlap gpt-5.5 v1	overlap gpt-5.5 v2	reverse overlap gpt-5.5 v2
mean	0.4614	0.4532	0.2544	0.3740	0.2363	0.3502
std	0.2724	0.2715	0.2926	0.3456	0.2777	0.3378
min	0.0058	0.0065	0.0000	0.0000	0.0019	0.0079
max	0.9219	0.9536	0.8831	1.0000	0.9167	1.0000

Table 2
Descriptive statistics for the overlap and reverse overlap of the generated routes with the manually drawn routes.

too far.“

3. Directions that include street names but do not actually lead in the specified direction; e.g., on a street running north-south, you should follow the direction east, which is not possible.
4. Seemingly random street names from the urban area of the origin or destination point are mentioned, which are neither related nor lead in the correct direction.
5. Information for navigation without street names, which refers to street signs or prominent landmarks but does not actually exist.

The problem of invalid routes generated by FMs is somewhat to be expected as they do not possess exact geometrical representation of the street network, but only the latent representations. It was apparent that they have potential to exhibit or at least mimic the local knowledge by stating a person should “roll down to Hauptplatz”, “watch out for pedestrians and trams” or even “take the Murradweg over the city route because it is greener and has less traffic”. However, all such suggestions lose meaning when the route suggests an impossible maneuver. One potential solution to the invalid routes issue is to develop an agentic approach where one agent would suggest a route and another would validate it. Alternatively, it may be feasible to develop a hybrid solution where routing engines would offer several shortest paths and FMs would enrich and optimize them with local knowledge.

Other limitations of this study are the limited OD pairs set (and POI variety), the assumption of homogeneous local preference (i.e., individuals may choose different routes), as well as the missing consideration of spatial variance of FM generated results, and the limited evaluation measures with no real world grounding of parameters such as travel time, perceived safety and comfort, and so on. To address these limitations, a wider comprehensive study with real-world experimentation, more FM models and prompting strategies like “Persona Prompting” and using multiple prompts for one OD pair to gain self consistency is needed.

In the broad field of investigating the capability of FMs to access and apply local knowledge we showed a very limited study on certain routing tasks. It showcases the potential added value in decision making for non-locals without having local knowledge themselves, but also the limitations especially in the geospatial context. It is important to investigate the alignment between FMs and local knowledge

further as FMs have the potential to improve the alignment of the solution to the user in almost all geospatial tasks and surpass the rigidity of existing deterministic modeling-based approaches.

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